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H2020-MSCA-RISE-2015
Project N° 690968

Nanomaterials-based innovative engineering solutions to ensure sustainable safeguard to indoor air

**RISE Marie Skłodowska-Curie Projects CONFERENCE &
SATELLITE WORKSHOPS**

ODAE 2019

**International Conference on Open Dialog in Applied Engineering: Recent
Advances and New Frontiers**

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Madeira, Portugal

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IMT Mines Alès
École Mines-Télécom

LABORATÓRIO NACIONAL DE ENGENHARIA CIVIL

NEW PROCESSES AND NEW MATERIALS FOR INDOOR AIR ANTIMICROBIAL CONDITIONING

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS:

**VIEGAS J.-C., LNEC, PORTUGAL; PINTO L., LNEC, PORTUGAL;
SABOURIN L., IMT MA, FRANCE; RAVEL R., IMT MA, FRANCE**

From the Conference Program:

Saturday, November 16

Boardroom of the Jacarandá, 16th floor hotel Savoy Palace

Av. do Infante 25, 9004-542 Funchal, Madeira

8:30- 10:10

Introduction to the Panel 2 discussion: Advance in Environmental Engineering

Keynote 7. Twin Presentation

CONCEPT “NANO GUARD2AR Innovation & Main Developments

Prof. Dr. Svitlana Lyubchyk, NOVA id FCT, Department of Chemistry, Faculdade de Ciência e Tecnologia, Universidade Nova de Lisboa, PORTUGAL

Full size prototype testing Current Progress

Eng. Dr. Joao Viegas, LNEC-Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil, PORTUGAL

Oral Presentation.

CEO Dr. Paulo Zaragoza Pedro, Ar Diagnostic Ltd., PORTUGAL

Airborne Pathogens and Indoor Air Quality Current

Prof. Alexey Evstratov, IMT INSTITUT MINES-TELECOM, FRANCE

New processes and new materials for indoor air antimicrobial conditioning

Chair – Prof. Dr. Paulo Mota, Universidade Nova de Lisboa, PORTUGAL

Outlook

1. Innovative nano - and microcomposite materials for the indoor air germicidal conditioning (concept of IMT Mines Alès).
2. Dark Operating Highly Interactive Selective Hole Generators and Dark Operating Mechanically Obstructive Materials: properties and main results of laboratory tests.
3. Dark Operating Mechanically Obstructive Materials: main results of pilot tests carried out at LNEC (June 2019).
4. Short conclusions and dissemination of the results obtained in the framework of the project H2020 MSCA-RISE-2015 NANOGUARD2AR.

Innovative nano- and microcomposite materials for the indoor air germicidal conditioning

1 Energetically-Dependent Germicidal Nano- and Microcomposites (ED-GNM)

2 Energetically-Independent Germicidal Nano- and Microcomposites (EI-GNM)

IMT Mines Alès - C2MA product series presented for the first time during the REA Monitoring Meeting on the advancement of the project H2020 MSCA-RISE-2015 NANO GUARD2AR held in Lisbon, Portugal, on May 19th, 2017

Slide n°5: main references (IMT Mines Ales contributions)

[1] Evstratov A., Interactive hole-selective nanocomposites as safe and easily-handling materials alternative to free nanoparticle photocatalysts, *Research report* on H2020 MSCA-RISE-2015 project “Nanomaterials-based innovative engineering solution to ensure sustainable safeguard to indoor air (NANO GUARD2AR)”, Proposal n° 690968, WP1 (Innovative NMs Composite Design), Deliverable D.1, Part 2, IMT Mines Ales, 2017, 25 p.

[23] Evstratov A., Sabourin L., Interactive Hole-Selective Nanocomposite Photocatalysts and Highly Innovative Dark-Operating Nanomaterials: Basic Concepts, *Research report* on H2020 MSCA-RISE-2015 project “Nanomaterials-based innovative engineering solution to ensure sustainable safeguard to indoor air (NANO GUARD2AR)”, Proposal n° 690968, WP1 (Innovative NMs Composite Design), Deliverable D.1, Part 1, IMT Mines Ales, 2016, 42 p.

[25] ADEME: Costarramone N., Lacombe S., Pécheyran C., Desauziers V., Evstratov A., Cantau C., Traitement de l'air intérieur par photocatalyse: Performance et innocuité de systèmes et matériaux photocatalytiques commerciaux, *Rapport de recherche*, Convention ADEME – IMT Mines Ales n°1362C0027, 2015, 164 p. (<https://www.ademe.fr/sites/default/files/assets/documents/traitement-air-interieur-performance-et-innocuite-systemes-et-materiaux-photocatalytiques-201508.pdf>).

[26] Evstratov A., Grishin A., Roux J.-C., Hadj Hassine A., Grigorev K., TCO Nanocomposites Anodes as Efficient Low-Tension Generators of Hydroxyl Radicals, *International Conference on Advanced Complex Inorganic Nanomaterials ACIN-2013 (July 15th-19th, 2013, Namur, Belgium)*, Sci. Program, Contribution P-065.

[27] Evstratov A., Grishin A., Roux J.-C., Conductor oxide nanocomposites as water supplied electric charge generators, *3rd European Conference on NanoFilms (July 07th-14th, 2014, Sevilla, Spain)*, Book of Abstracts (<http://ecnf.al-nanofunc.eu/docs/book-of-abstracts-vonline.pdf>), pp. 58 – 59.

[28] Majoli L., Evstratov A., Guillot J.-M., Rouvière A., Baussand P., Composite Carbon Nanostructures as Promising Carriers for Gas Analysis, *9th World Nanotechnology Conference NSTI Nanotech – 2006 (May 7th – 11th, 2006, Boston, USA)*, Proceedings, Volume 1, p. 146 – 149.

Laboratory dynamic tests of Dark Operating Germicidal Composite Materials: applied equipment

Front view of sample holders

Dark Operating Highly Interactive Selective Hole Generators (EI-GNM-HI-FCCG-Sh⁺-DOM): principal properties _ 1

- Chemical composition: MnO₂/AlPO₄/γ-Al₂O₃ (support) (example: 4.5 % ms./32.3 % ms./63.2 % ms. (support)).

Results of the EDX (at the left) and SEM (at the right) analyses.

- Morphology: spherical alumina beads \varnothing 2.5 – 3.0 mm covered with AlPO₄ (1st massive layer) and with MnO₂ (2nd island-type layer) using the wet impregnation method.

Dark Operating Highly Interactive Selective Hole Generators (EI-GNM-HI-FCCG-Sh⁺-DOM): principal properties _ 2

Agar diffusion inhibitory tests results (static operation conditions):

Incubated Petri dishes containing *B. atrophaeus* being in contact with a, b) $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ beads; c, d) $\text{ZnO}/\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ beads and e, f) $\text{MnO}_2/\text{AlPO}_4/\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ beads.

Inhibition radii obtained by agar diffusion inhibitory tests:

	$\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ beads	$\text{ZnO}/\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ beads	$\text{MnO}_2/\text{AlPO}_4/\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ beads
Inhibition radius of the first plate	0 mm	0 mm	9 mm
Inhibition radius of the second plate	0 mm	0 mm	9 mm
Mean inhibition radius	0 mm	0 mm	9 mm

Dark Operating Highly Interactive Selective Hole Generators (EI-GNM-HI-FCCG-Sh⁺-DOM): principal properties _ 3

It is supposed that in order to be able to manifest the germicidal ability after the results exposed at the previous slide the tested material has to proceed the following surface reactions:

However, the applied active component, $\beta\text{-MnO}_2$, in its free state can not favor the reaction (3) because of a relatively great stability of the solvated forms of hydroxyl anions unable to stay single (non-hydrated) in humid media. For instance, the most probable monohydrated complex $[\text{HO}^-\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ in order to be transferred in its active radical form requires the energy near to 3.0 eV (D.W. Arnold, C. Xu, D.M. Neumark, *J. Chem. Phys.*, **102** (15), p. 6089, 1995).

← The hydrated hydroxide ion H_3O_2^-

Dark Operating Highly Interactive Selective Hole Generators (EI-GNM-HI-FCCG-Sh⁺-DOM): principal properties _ 4

In fact, the transparency for an electron of a 2D (flat) rectangular potential barrier—in particular, of a bandgap—in the simplest case can be evaluated as follows:

$$D = D_0 * e^{\frac{-2d}{\hbar} \sqrt{2m_e(U_0 - E)}},$$

where D —coefficient of transparency to be determined ($0 < D \leq 1$); D_0 —coefficient of transparency without any energetic barrier to overcome ($D_0 = 1$); m_e —masse of electron ($9.11 \cdot 10^{-31}$ kg); \hbar —reduced Planck constant ($\hbar = h / 2\pi = 1.05 \cdot 10^{-34}$ J·s); ($U_0 - E$)—difference between the barrier's height and the electron's energy, eV; d —thickness of the barrier, nm.

The following variables can be used as basic data:

- ($U_0 - E$) = 0.25 eV, where $U_0 = 0.25$ eV (the bandgap energetic barrier),
- $E = 0$ eV (the worst virtual case when the electron's own energy is not taken into consideration),
- $d = 2.21$ Å or 0.221 nm (the length of Mn_{CB}-O_{VB} bond in MnO₂ [30], where the indications “CB”, “VB” signify the ion's position in the conduction band and in the valence band, respectively).

The calculation results show that D value reaches for β -MnO₂ 0.32 or 32% (explain what does it mean)

For β -
MnO₂

Dark Operating Highly Interactive Selective Hole Generators (EI-GNM-HI-FCCG-Sh⁺-DOM): principal properties _ 5

Pure β -MnO₂ is thus unable to proceed the reactions (1 – 3) cited on the slide n° 9 because of the hydrated complex [HO·H₂O] energetic stability is greater than the maximal excitation energy (0.25 – 0.28 eV) which can be fulfilled to an adsorbed species by the surface of manganese dioxide.

However, for a donor-acceptor composite material MnO₂/AlPO₄/ γ -Al₂O₃ the situation can be radically changed:

Donor oxide component (D) and its acceptor support (A)	β -MnO ₂ (D)	Al ₂ O ₃ (A)	P ₄ O ₁₀ (A) (model of PO ₄ ³⁻)
Absolute HOMO position corresponding to the oxide's work function, eV	(- 6.50) [29]	(- 12.15) [41]	(- 13.84) [41]
Relative HOMO position $\Delta E_{\text{HOMO}} = \text{HOMO}_{\text{MnO}_2} - \text{HOMO}_A$, eV	-	5.65	> 7.30
Estimative energy of electron holes h ⁺ occurring in the donor's valence band VB _{MnO2} for pure β -MnO ₂ and for its donor-acceptor composites (separately for MnO ₂ /Al ₂ O ₃ and for MnO ₂ /AlPO ₄), eV	0.25–0.28 $E_{h^+ \text{ MnO}_2} = \text{LUMO}_{\text{MnO}_2} - \text{HOMO}_{\text{MnO}_2}$ [25, 29, 30, 31]	5.65 $E_{h^+ \text{ MnO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3} = \text{HOMO}_{\text{MnO}_2} - \text{HOMO}_{\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3}$	> 7.30 $E_{h^+ \text{ MnO}_2/\text{AlPO}_4} = \text{HOMO}_{\text{MnO}_2} - \text{HOMO}_{\text{P}_2\text{O}_{10}}$ (model)

LUMO—Lowest Unoccupied Molecular Orbitals.

(Dutheil de la Rochère A., Evstartov A., Bayle S., *et al.*, *PLoS ONE*, 2019, 14, n°10, 21 p.; doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0224114)

Dark Operating Highly Interactive Selective Hole Generators (EI-GNM-HI-FCCG-Sh⁺-DOM): principal properties _ 6

Donor-acceptor composites $\text{MnO}_2/\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and $\text{MnO}_2/\text{AlPO}_4/\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ are extremely efficient in creation of high energy holes at their surfaces under dark operating conditions, without any complementary energetic assistance.

Dark Operating Mechanically Obstructive Materials (EI-GNM-MO-DOM): principal properties

- **Chemical composition:** ZnO/ γ -Al₂O₃ (support) (example: 41.9 % ms./58.1 % ms./63.2 % ms. (support)).

"Knife-and-needle"
surface microstructures

Results of the EDX (at the left) and SEM (at the right) analyses.

- **Morphology:** spherical alumina beads \varnothing 2.5 – 3.0 mm covered with ZnO using the method of thermal synthesis in aqueous solution.

Dark Operating Germicidal Composite Materials, EI-GNM-HI-FCCG-Sh⁺-DOM and EI-GNM-MO-DOM : main results of laboratory dynamic tests _ 1

Airborne
bacteria

Test of the germicidal efficiency of materials in dynamic operating conditions.
(air linear velocity: 0.2 m/s)

MnO₂/AlPO₄/γ-Al₂O₃ manifests the best germicidal performance.

Dark Operating Germicidal Composite Materials, EI-GNM-HI-FCCG-Sh⁺-DOM and EI-GNM-MO-DOM : main results of laboratory dynamic tests _ 2

Airborne
bacteria

Test of the germicidal efficiency of materials in dynamic operating conditions.
(air linear velocity: 0.7 m/s)

MnO₂/AlPO₄/γ-Al₂O₃ and ZnO/γ-Al₂O₃ germicidal performances are quite similar.

Dark Operating Germicidal Composite Materials, EI-GNM-HI-FCCG-Sh⁺-DOM and EI-GNM-MO-DOM : main results of laboratory dynamic tests _ 3

Airborne
bacteria

Test of the germicidal efficiency of materials in dynamic operating conditions.
(air linear velocity: 1.0–1.2 m/s)

The germicidal activity of ZnO/ γ -Al₂O₃ begins to overcome the one of MnO₂/AlPO₄/ γ -Al₂O₃.

Dark Operating Germicidal Composite Materials, EI-GNM-HI-FCCG-Sh⁺-DOM and EI-GNM-MO-DOM : main results of laboratory dynamic tests _ 4

Airborne
bacteria

Test of the germicidal efficiency of materials in dynamic operating conditions.
(air linear velocity: 2.0–2.2 m/s)

ZnO/ γ -Al₂O₃ manifests the best germicidal performance.

Dark Operating Mechanically Obstructive Materials

(EI-GNM-MO-DOM): main results of pilot tests carried out at LNEC (June 2019) _ 1

Functional scheme of the pilot installation

General view of the pilot installation

Dark Operating Mechanically Obstructive Materials

(EI-GNM-MO-DOM): main results of pilot tests carried out at LNEC (June 2019) _ 2

Operating principle of the LNEC air curtain

Dark Operating Mechanically Obstructive Materials

(EI-GNM-MO-DOM): main results of pilot tests carried out at LNEC (June 2019) _ 3

Air curtain turbine with damper setting facilities

Test installation assembled and tested in the premises of LNEC (general view):
a – air curtain; b – coupling element (ventilation duct); c – dark-operating test unit
of IMT Mines Alès.

Dark Operating Mechanically Obstructive Materials

(EI-GNM-MO-DOM): main results of pilot tests carried out at LNEC (June 2019) _ 4

Airborne
bacteria

Evolution of the concentrations of airborne micro-organisms in time in the indoor air of the test chamber ($53 m^3$) at the gas linear velocity ω approximately equal to $1.0 m/s$ (gas flow rate – $36 m^3/h$):

blue curve – mode 1 (no active material); red curve – mode 2 ($\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$);
green curve – mode 3 ($\text{ZnO}/\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$)

Dark Operating Mechanically Obstructive Materials

(EI-GNM-MO-DOM): main results of pilot tests carried out at LNEC (June 2019) _ 5

Airborne
bacteria

Evolution of the concentrations of airborne micro-organisms in time in the indoor air of the test chamber ($53 m^3$) at the gas linear velocity ω approximately equal to $2.6 m/s$ (gas flow rate – $90 m^3/h$):

blue curve – mode 2 ($\gamma-Al_2O_3$); red curve – mode 3 ($ZnO/\gamma-Al_2O_3$).

Dark Operating Mechanically Obstructive Materials

(EI-GNM-MO-DOM): main results of pilot tests carried out at LNEC (June 2019) _ 6

As compared to the test series carried out at the gas linear velocity approximately equal to 1.0 m/s , at the one of 2.6 m/s the volumetric gas flow rate has been increased to an unacceptable value equal to 25 s^{-1} or $90\,000 \text{ h}^{-1}$.

It is considered undesirable to carry out any gas treatment processes in such conditions because of low performances caused by extremely short contact times and very high energetic losses: 890 Pa ($91 \text{ mm H}_2\text{O}$) at $\omega = 1.0 \text{ m/s}$ and 5560 Pa ($567 \text{ mm H}_2\text{O}$) at $\omega = 2.5 \text{ m/s}$ (ΔP differ more than 6 times (!)).

Based on the results obtained in this series of experiments, it can be concluded that the application of a mechanically-obstructive dark-operation germicidal composite $\text{ZnO}/\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ seems to be justified, taking into account both the technical and economic points of view, at moderate dynamic conditions which comprise the average gas flow linear velocity inside the active material bed occurring in the vicinity of 1.0 m/s , with conceivable deviations from the modal value (20 – 25 %).

Short conclusions

Dark-operating selective hole / hydroxyl radical generators (example – $\text{MnO}_2/\text{AlPO}_4/\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$) and dark-operating mechanically obstructive composite materials (example – $\text{ZnO}/\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$) can be applied as germicidal agents for the indoor air antimicrobial conditioning.

As compared to the test series carried out at the gas linear velocity approximately equal to 1.0 m/s , at the one of 2.6 m/s the volumetric gas flow rate has been increased to an unacceptable value equal to 25 s^{-1} or $90\,000 \text{ h}^{-1}$.

It is considered undesirable to carry out any gas treatment processes in such conditions because of low performances caused by extremely short contact times and very high energetic losses: 890 Pa ($91 \text{ mm H}_2\text{O}$) at $\omega = 1.0 \text{ m/s}$ and 5560 Pa ($567 \text{ mm H}_2\text{O}$) at $\omega = 2.5 \text{ m/s}$ (ΔP differ more than 6 times (!)).

Based on the results obtained in this series of experiments, it can be concluded that the application of a mechanically-obstructive dark-operation germicidal composite $\text{ZnO}/\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ seems to be justified, taking into account both the technical and economic points of view, at moderate dynamic conditions which comprise the average gas flow linear velocity inside the active material bed occurring in the vicinity of 1.0 m/s , with conceivable deviations from the modal value (20 – 25 %).

Dissemination of the results obtained in the framework of the project H2020 MSCA-RISE-2015 NANOGUARD2AR _ 1

1. Chauvin A., Evstratov A., Bayle S., Sabourin L., Indoor Air Disinfection in Dynamic Dark Operating Conditions, *5th International Conference on Advances in Chemical Engineering and Technology* (October 04th – 05th, 2018, London, United Kingdom), Proceedings, p. 41 (+ conference); abstract according to <https://chemicalengineering.insightconferences.com/abstract/2018/indoor-air-disinfection-in-dynamic-dark-operating-conditions>); this contribution is referred in *Journal of Advanced Chemical Engineering (J Adv Chem Eng)*, 2018, **8**; doi: 10.4172/2090-4568-C3-011.
2. Dutheil de la Rochère A., Evstratov A., Sabourin L., Bayle S., Matériaux nanocomposites germicides pour l'assainissement de l'air intérieur, *Grand congrès unitaire de la Fédération Française des Matériaux MATERIAUX-2018* (19 – 23 novembre 2018, Strasbourg, France), Programme, p. 57.
3. Evstratov A., Sabourn L., Ledoux V., Sol-Gel Revitalization of Porous Refractory Ceramics, 20th Intern. Sol-Gel Conference (August 25th – 30th, 2019, Saint-Petersburg, Russia), Book of Abstracts, p. 145.
4. Dutheil de la Rochère A., Evstratov A., Bayle S., Sabourin L., Frering A., Lopez-Cuesta J.-M., Exploring the antimicrobial properties of dark-operating ceramic-based nanocomposite materials for the disinfection of indoor air, *PLoS ONE*, 2019, **14**, n°10, 21 p.; doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0224114.

Dissemination of the results obtained in the framework of the project H2020 MSCA-RISE-2015 NANOGUARD2AR _ 2

5. Evstratov A., Dutheil de la Rochère A., Bayle S., Lopez-Cuesta J.-M., Ruffieux M., New processes and new materials for indoor air antimicrobial conditioning, *Open Dialog in Applied Engineering: Recent Advances and New Frontiers (Intern. Conf. and Satellite Workshops on the projects H2020 MSCA-RISE-2015 n°690968, n°601010 and H2020 MSCA-RISE-2016 n°734641)*, ODAE 2019 (November 14th – 17th, Funchal, Madeira, Portugal), Sci. Program (<http://www.eng-oda2019.org/>).
6. Interactive Hole-Selective Nanocomposite Photocatalysts and Highly Innovative Dark-Operating Nanomaterials: basic concepts, *Deliverable D1.1 Sci. Report WP1 Innovative NMs Composite Design, Project NANOGUARD2AR* / Evstratov A., IMT Mines Alès, 2016, 35 p., annex.
7. Interactive Hole-Selective Nanocomposites as Safe and Easily-Handling Materials Alternative to Free Nanoparticle Photocatalysts, *Deliverable D1.2 Sci. Report WP1 Innovative NMs Composite Design, Project NANOGUARD2AR* / Evstratov A., IMT Mines Alès, 2017, 25 p.
8. Designed Dark-Operating NM-driven unit, *Deliverable D2.2 Sci. Report WP2 NMs and Air Curtain System Units Design, Project NANOGUARD2AR* / Evstratov A., Sabourin L., Chauvin A., IMT Mines Alès, 2017, 26 p.
9. A MnO₂-based interactive ROS generator and a ZnO-based desert-rose-shaped cellular destructor as innovative dark-operating germicidal materials (DOGM) conceived and applied for antimicrobial indoor air conditioning, *Contribution to WP3 System Units Testing, Project NANOGUARD2AR* / Dutheil de la Rochère A., Evstratov A., Sabourin L., Bayle S., Frering A., IMT Mines Alès, 2018, 11 p.

Dissemination of the results obtained in the framework of the project H2020 MSCA-RISE-2015 NANOGUARD2AR _ 3

10. Energetically-independent dark-operating germicidal composites materials for the indoor air sanitation, *Contribution to WP4 Prototype System Elaboration (Assembling), Project NANOGUARD2AR* / Evstratov A., Dutheil de la Rochère A., Ravel R., Sabourin L., Bayle S., Lopez-Cuesta J.-M., IMT Mines Alès, 2019, 21 p.

**THANK YOU
FOR YOUR ATTENTION**